

Practice Abstract no. 50

FOODITY - Open Call #2 project - ONCONOURISH

The FOODITY project launched the second of its two open calls in May 2024 and closed in July 2024. The FOODITY project selected six innovative data-driven projects that develop solutions contributing to more sustainable food systems while boosting citizen data sovereignty. Starting in November 2024, the six projects will receive up to €187,500 to develop their project activities.

One of the selected projects is "ONCONOURISH: AI-based Dietary Optimizer for Cancer patients."

Profile

Project acronym / title	ONCONOURISH AI-based Dietary Optimizer for Cancer patients
Partners (country)	IBIONS (Spain), Datipic (Spain), TheMovemen (Spain)
Project area	Education

Context

Cancer is a widespread disease, ultimately affecting one in two individuals. While the positive impact of nutritional counseling on quality of life and mortality is well-established, it is not a standard component of hospital cancer care, with less than a third of patients seeking it. Acknowledging this problem, the EU has called for the mandatory integration of nutritional support into cancer treatment (as outlined in [resolution 2020/2267, INI](#)).

Cancer patients often struggle to achieve the best possible treatment outcomes because they are not able to fully leverage scientifically validated therapeutic tools, particularly in nutrition. Recognising this challenge, the medical-scientific based team of IBIONS offers cancer patients guidance on nutritional adjustments, grounded in the latest scientific evidence, to amplify the effectiveness of hospital treatments, mitigate side effects, and ultimately enhance their prognosis and quality of life.

Despite the identified benefits, an obstacle to successful dietary modification remains: the inherent challenge cancer patients face in sustaining new nutritional protocols due to deeply ingrained, lifelong eating habits. To address this challenge, ONCONOURISH proposes an AI-based dietary optimiser solution using nutritional logs for cancer patients ensuring it meets patients' needs. The solution aims to improve adherence to nutritional protocols by providing personalised feedback and recommendations. The solution incorporates cognitive-behavioral strategies and employs AI technology, which is not yet widely deployed, particularly in the context of cancer treatment, making it a groundbreaking addition to the field.

Objectives

The general objective of the ONCONOURISH project is to improve the quality of life and treatment outcomes for cancer patients by improving dietary adherence through an AI-based tool.

Specific objectives of the project include:

- **Tool Development:** Build an AI-powered system allowing patients and/or their caregivers to enter weekly dietary logs via images, text messages, or voice recordings. The system will use advanced technologies in computer vision and natural language processing (NLP) to accurately capture and log the food intake, ensuring a comprehensive dietary record.
- **Develop AI algorithms** that analyse the entered records to determine if all nutritional needs are met according to pre-established criteria. Advanced algorithms and machine learning models, including NLP and deep learning techniques, process both textual and visual data to identify nutritional content, deficiencies, and excesses. The system generates detailed reports highlighting dietary strengths and areas for improvement, providing personalised feedback and actionable insights.
- **Develop an AI-driven feedback system:** Involves providing detailed, personalised feedback based on the nutritional analysis of users' dietary intake, explaining why certain foods should be added or removed and their health impacts.
- **Develop an AI-driven system that generates personalized recipes:** Involves using AI to provide new recipes, recommended foods, and adaptable weekly menus, simplifying healthy eating for users. The system will leverage advanced machine learning algorithms and NLP techniques to create personalized, nutritionally balanced meal plans tailored to individual dietary needs and preferences.
- **Create a reward system to increase patient engagement and improve adherence to nutritional changes:** Involves integrating a gamification component into the AI-driven platform to boost user engagement and adherence to dietary recommendations. The system will incorporate a reward mechanism that recognizes and rewards patients for achieving their dietary goals and following nutritional protocols.
- **Provide a user-friendly interface for patients and caregivers to input and track dietary data:** Centred on designing an intuitive and easy-to-use interface that allows patients and caregivers to log and monitor dietary data effortlessly. The interface will be developed with user experience in mind and by co-development with cancer patients, featuring clear navigation, simple input methods, and visual aids to track progress.

Impact

The pilot phase of the ONCONOURISH project will involve deploying the AI-based dietary optimiser with a selected group of cancer patients. The expected results include increased adherence to nutritional protocols, improved patient outcomes measured by the QLQ-C301 questionnaire (developed by the European Organization for Research and Treatment of Cancer), an improved understanding of the role of nutrition in cancer treatment, and increased sustainability of dietary advice, making it more affordable and reducing the economic burden after cancer diagnosis.

Other specific impacts aligned with the FOODITY project include:

- **Fostering open data systems:** The project contributes to the objective of fostering open data systems by incorporating patient dietary data into the FOODITY Data Lake. This data can be anonymised and shared with researchers and other stakeholders to advance nutritional science and develop new dietary interventions.
- **Empowering citizens on data sovereignty:** By using the FOODITY dataU solution, patients have full control over their data, including who it is shared with and for how long. This empowerment aligns with FOODITY's aim to enhance data sovereignty for citizens.
- **Environmentally friendly and sustainable food systems:** ONCONOURISH promotes sustainable food systems by recommending a mediterranean-based diet, locally sourced and seasonal ingredients in the personalised dietary plans. This approach not only supports local economies but also reduces the carbon footprint associated with food transportation.
- **Contribution to the EU's FOOD 2030 research and innovation policy:** The project supports the EU's FOOD 2030 policy by advancing personalised nutrition, promoting healthy eating habits, and ensuring food security through data-driven approaches to nutrition and health.

